

Munir's Socio-eco-environmental Approach to Environmental Education

Note: The Fellows of the Georg Eckert Institute, Germany, and the IRC (International Rescue Committee), valued this model.

Munir's socio-eco-environmental approach is a conceptual model of environmental education for communities, living under emergencies.

Developing environmental literacy programs that support sustainable educational practices should begin with considering socio-economic elements. A scoping review can help to understand how the socio-cultural, and political geography of ABC country shapes the ways people interact with each other and their environments.

Once this initial understanding has been established, we need to explore the socio-psychological trauma and healing mechanisms through the lens of local people.

This involves (1) examining the mental health challenges faced by learners during man-made disasters and environmental catastrophes; (2) resources/platforms availability; (3) how these resources/platforms contribute to their well-being; (4) existing gaps. A range of strategies can be employed for this purpose, including ethnography, interviews, drawing, and photovoice.

The next step is to check the current state of environmental literacy through a desk review and content analysis, followed by behavioral mapping. This involves assessing the existing knowledge, skills, and attitudes related to environmental issues, and exploring ecological identity and environmental practices.

To develop a contextual course on environmental literacy, a design thinking approach that integrates empathy mapping and ethnography should be employed. This will enable the identification of socio-cultural, educational, and environmental challenges from the perspective of the actual participants who will benefit from the course. Additionally, it is important to shift away from anthropocentrism towards ecocentrism when drafting a course.

Overall, the process of developing environmental literacy programs that support sustainable educational practice should start with an understanding of socioeconomic elements, followed by exploring the socio-psychological trauma and healing mechanisms experienced by the community.

Scope Review

Water Resources

Socio-cultural Environment

Political Geography Geographical Location Climate and Weather

ethnography, interviews, drawing, and photovoice

Desk Review

State of Environmental Literacy

Awareness

Skills

Attitudes

Ecological Identity Exploration

Design thinking approach (Empathy map)

Course Designing

Community-based Participatory Research

Shift from anthropocentrism to ecocentricism

Socio-cultural, educational, environmental challenges through ethnographic approach